

Conference Abstract

Assessing the use of Small Inland Wetlands by fish in the Lower Tagus Basin (Portugal)

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Received: 20 Nov 2025 | Published: 30 Dec 2025

Citation: Ribeiro D, Dias D, Gago J, Martelo J, Rivaes R, da Costa L, Santos D, Ribeiro F, Catalão J, Magalhães M (2025) Assessing the use of Small Inland Wetlands by fish in the Lower Tagus Basin (Portugal).

ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e179209. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e179209>

Abstract

Inland wetlands have long been recognized as important biodiversity hotspots and amongst the most impacted ecosystems worldwide, requiring urgent conservation management and restoration. However, focus has been mostly on wetland use by iconic birds and mammals, largely ignoring other highly endangered animals, such as fish. The Tagus Basin harbours the most diverse regional pool of freshwater fish in Portugal, with a total of 28 native species, 2 of which are Lusitanian endemics. In particular, the Lisbon arched-mouth nase (*Iberochondrostoma olisiponense*) is strongly associated to small inland wetlands and restricted to the Lower Tagus basin. Multiple wetlands were historically found in this region, with periodic floods inundating the riverside floodplain. However significant changes in land and water uses have occurred, potentially affecting the spatial availability, distribution and dynamics of small wetlands and their use by fish. Here we aimed to identify small inland wetlands in the Lower Tagus Basin (Portugal) and assess local fish communities. Using the Sentinel-2 imagery combined with Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), a total of 409 small wetlands were identified in the Lower Tagus basin, 30 of which were persistent and showed potential to host fish. From these, 10 wetlands covering the perceived variability in environmental conditions and

distributed across the basin were sampled for fish. Data obtained using multiple sampling techniques were combined using the Gear Mean Standardization (MGMS) approach, and related to habitat, landscape, and land use variables using Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA). Fish communities included five native species, but were dominated by eight non-native species. Fish community structure was significantly related to habitat depth and wetland connectivity to the Tagus river, and showed no measurable association with land uses. Isolated, deep wetlands were mostly used by angling non-native species such as Largemouth bass (*Micropterus nigricans*) and Pumpkinseed sunfish (*Lepomis gibbosus*). Wetlands most connected to the Tagus mainstem, harboured mobile species such as Iberian barbel (*Luciobarbus bocagei*) and Thinlip grey mullet (*Chelon ramada*). Shallow wetlands were habitat for threatened European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*), and Lisbon arched-mouthed nase. Our results indicate that small inland wetlands may act as refuges for threatened fish species, and should be managed and restored to help hamper fish diversity loss. However, connected wetlands they may also provide potential spreading hotspots for non-native fish, and should thus require population eradication and control programs to help boost native fish diversity.

Keywords

Remote Sensing, *Iberochondrostoma olisiponense*, Endangered Fish, Invasive Fish, Freshwater Biodiversity

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Presented at

International Conference: "The Fish of Muddy Waters"

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.